

STUDIES OF THE EFFECT OF CARBON BLACK PARTICLES ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SBR/NR BLENDS USED IN PASSENGER TIRE TREADS.

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ABSTRACT

In this study, 20 recipe rubber compounds were prepared by using SMR-20 type of natural rubber and SBR-1502 type of styrene-butadiene rubber in different levels (0, 25, 50, 75 and 100) pphr and each recipe reinforced with carbon black at different ratio (20, 40, 60 and 80) pphr (part per hundred). The mechanical properties – such as tensile strength, tensile modulus at 100% elongation, elongation at break, hardness, wear and resilience were studied. The results show that the tensile modulus at 100% elongation (MOD 100) and ultimate tensile strength increase with increasing of carbon black loading level and maximum value was achieved at 60 pphr (carbon black), while elongation at break decreased with increasing of carbon black loading for all recipes. All these properties increased with increasing of NR to SBR. The hardness and wear properties of the NR/SBR blends with the increment of SBR percentages and carbon black loading level were greatly enhanced. The resilience decrease with increase of carbon black loading for all recipes and with the increase of SBR to NR.

Keywords: **Elastomer blend, Carbon Black, Mechanical Properties, Resilience.**

دراسة تأثير حبيبات اسود الكربون على الخصائص الميكانيكية لخلائط المطاط (الصناعي/الطبيعي) المستخدمة في صناعة نقشة الاطارات.

الخلاصة:

تم في هذا البحث تحضير (20) عجنه حضرت بواسطة استخدام المطاط الطبيعي نوع (SMR20) ومطاط الستايرين بيوتادين نوع (1502) بنسب تحميل مختلفة (0، 25، 50، 75، 100) وكل خلطة مقواة باسود الكربون وبنسب تحميل مختلفة (20، 40، 60، 80). تم اجراء العديد من الاختبارات الميكانيكية لغرض تحديد خواص المادة المتراكبة المحضرة، مثل (مقاومة الشد، معامل الشد عند نسبة 100% استطالة، الاستطالة عند الكسر، الصلادة، البلى والارتدادية). حيث نلاحظ ان معامل الشد عند 100% استطاله ومقاومة الشد القصوى تزداد مع زيادة اسود الكربون وتعلى قيمه كانت عند 60 pphr من اسود الكربون بينما انخفضت الاستطاله عند الكسر لجميع الخلائط. حيث ان جميع هذه الخواص ازدادت مع زيادة مستوى المطاط الطبيعي الى الصناعي. الصلادة وخواص البلى لجميع الخلائط ازدادت مع زيادة مستوى المطاط الصناعي الى الطبيعي ومع زيادة اسود الكربون، اما الارتدادية فقد انخفضت مع زيادة اسود الكربون وزيادة مستوى المطاط الصناعي الى الطبيعي لجميع الخلائط.

INTRODUCTION

Blending of two or more types of polymer is a useful technique for preparation and developing materials with properties superior to those of individual constituents ; this statement is also true with rubber blends, especially in tire manufacture [F. Findik 2004 and Kaushik Pal 2009] . Styrene Butadiene Rubber (SBR) is now the most common synthetic rubber being used in tires. It is made by polymerizing Styrene and Butadiene together; it is also possible by changing styrene content and polymerization process to make various types of SBR's with different characteristic [Toyo Tire Talk]. Natural rubber (NR) is known to exhibit numerous outstanding properties, such as good oil resistance, low gas permeability, improved wet grip and rolling resistance, coupled with high strength; having properties resembling those of synthetic rubbers. Natural rubber coming from latex is mostly polymerized isoprene with a small percentage of impurities in it. This will limit the range of properties available to it, although addition of sulfur and vulcanization is used to improve the mechanical and physical properties. Chemically, natural rubber is cis- 1,4-polyisoprene and occurs in Hevea rubber trees [Kaushik Pal 2010 and C.A. Harper 2000]. To improve the mechanical and physical properties of vulcanized rubber compounds, carbon black has been traditionally used as a major reinforcing material together with a few minor reinforcing materials such as clay, calcium carbonate and silicates since the excellent reinforcement with carbon black for rubbers was elucidated in early twentieth century, of which the most important reinforcement, reduction in material costs, and improvements in processing. Reinforcement is primarily enhancement of strength and strength related properties such as abrasion resistance, hardness, and modulus. A wide variety of particulate fillers is used in the rubber industry for various purposes [Kaushik pal 2010 and Heinrich 2002]. The use of carbon black is synonymous with the history of tires. However, the primary properties of carbon blacks are normally controlled by particle size, surface area, structure and surface activity which in most cases are interrelated [Chung Ho Shin 2008].

The idea of blending synthetic rubbers with natural rubber is certainly not a new one, but now it can be applied positively, by using new techniques developed over the last 5 years. These compounds are capable of forming a chemical link between these dissimilar rubbers to produce a technologically compatible blend. The blend vulcanizates produced exhibit enhanced physical properties by judicious selection of the SBR: NR ratio [Kaushik Pal 2009 and Naskar N 2001]. Blending of (SBR) and other types of rubber and its performance have been studied earlier, they have demonstrated that the physical properties of such blends can be significantly improved by adding a suitable compatibiliser [Pham Thi Hao 2001, A.A. Basfar 2002 and A. Mostafa 2009].

This work aims at improve the recipe properties of tire tread by adding the reinforcing fillers (carbon black) at different loading level in addition to the additive materials like (ZnO, steric acid, sulfur...etc) to elastomers styrene butadiene rubber SBR and natural rubber NR separately and blends of (SBR/NR) at different ratio. To optimize:

- The effect of the blending and loading in phr of NR with SBR.
- The effect of loading level of carbon black (N220).

These properties are: modulus of elasticity, ultimate tensile strength, elongation percentage at break, hardness: shore (A) and International Rubber Hardness Degree (IRHD), rebound resilience, abrasion wear resistance.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

All materials used in this research come from al Dewania factory for tire manufacture, Iraq. The structure of these materials is as follows

- Styrene- Butadiene Rubber (SBR), with Styrene content 23.5%: Moony viscosity at 100 °C = 50; specific gravity 0.94 (g/cm³); ash content 1%.
- Natural Rubber (NR), with specific gravity 0.934 (g/cm³); ash content 1%.
- Carbon black (N220): Black granulated powder has Pour Density 345 ± 30, (kg/m³). External Surface Area 111 ± 5 (m²/g) DBP absorption number 114 ± 4 (cm³/100 g).
- N-cyclohexyl-2-benzothiazole sulfonamide (Vulkacit CZ): pale grey; non hygroscopic powder; melting point 95–100 °C and specific gravity 1.27–1.31 (g/ cm³).
- Antioxidant (TMQ): specific gravity 1.08 (g /cm³)
- Antiozonant (6PPD) is a material of composition [N-(1, 3- dimethylbutyl)-N-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine]: specific gravity 1.0 (g / cm³).
- Sulfur: Pale yellow powder of sulfur element; purity 99.9%; melting point 112 °C; specific gravity 2.04– 2.06 (g/ cm³).
- Zinc oxide: fine powder; purity 99 %; specific gravity 5.6 (g/cm³).
- Stearic acid: melting point 67–69 °C; specific gravity 0.838 (g /cm³).

Recipes Formulation Used In This Work

The rubber compounds used in this work were prepared from natural rubber (SMR-20) and styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR-1502). Twenty carbon black (N220) filled recipes with other compounding materials such as filler; vulcanizing agent (sulfur) and accelerator were prepared with the compound formulations given in **Table 1**.

Mixing and Mastication

Mixing and mastication are conveniently done using two roll mills (Calender) and or internal mixer called (Banbury); the first one is used in this work. The mixing operation was executed on two stages, as shown in **Table 2**. The first one called *master batch* consist of rubbers (including reclaimed), activators, Antioxidant / Antiozonants, reinforcing agent carbon black and processed oil. At the end of the first stage carbon black blended with process oil in order to have optimum dispersion and coupling with rubber. The second stage is called the *final batch*. It consists of the previous master batch, curing agent (Sulfur), retarder and accelerators. These materials are added at the end of process to prevent pre-vulcanization which may occur due to the elevated temperatures, the test specimens were die cut from test slabs.

MEASUREMENT OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Tensile Test

The tensile properties (modulus at 100% elongation, tensile strength and elongation at break) of the rubber vulcanizates were tested according to ASTM D412-98 for (20) different samples at 20°C, with the use of dumbbell shaped samples. The applied force was (1KN) with a pulling device velocity (20 mm/ min). The tests being carried out using the microcomputer controlled electronic universal testing machine Model (WDW-50E).

Hardness Test

In this work the hardness is done by using two different measurements shore A and International Rubber Hardness Degree (IRHD) and according to ASTM D 2240 and D1415 respectively. The specimen should be at least 6 mm in thickness, the surface on which the measurement was made had to be flat and the lateral dimension of the specimen had to be sufficient to permit measurements at least 12 mm from the edges.

Abrasion Wear Resistance

This test is presented according to ASTM D 5963. The pin-on-disk abrasive wear tester is used. An abrasive paper (SiC) with a particle size of (200 μm) is pasted on a revolving disk. The applied load was (5 N) and the time was (15 min) for each one.

Resilience Test

This test is carried out according to BS (903), by using the (Wallace Dunlope Tripsometer) with data computer, which automatically computes resilience and displays as a percentage on a digital readout.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The tensile test involves an axial tensile load being applied to standard tensile specimens to obtain the (stress–strain) curves. The ultimate tensile strength, tensile modulus at (100%) elongation and elongation percentage at break obtained from this test.

Fig. 1 shows the relationship between the tensile modulus and the loading level of carbon black (N220) at 100% elongation for SBR and NR at different blends. This figure shows that the tensile modulus increases with the increase of the loading level of carbon black with a non-linear relationship and the maximum value can be achieved at (60) pphr of carbon black (N220) after that the tensile modulus will decrease with increase of the loading level of carbon black. The increasing of the tensile modulus with carbon black increment was due to the bonding force between the carbon black and rubber molecules prohibiting the movement of the rubber chain and reduced chain slippage and on the other hand because of the probability for the formation of a filler network enhanced with further increase in loading which is caused by a closer distance between aggregates in the rubber system and a better filler-filler interaction [Pham Thi Hao 2001, Saowaroj Chuayjuljit 2002 and Shuangye Dai 2007].

The decrease in the modulus of elasticity with increasing of carbon black after (60) pphr may be due to the further loaded carbon black could stiffen rubber by replacing with rigid and non-deformable particles, which yielded higher modulus. The occluded rubber, the amount of which increased with further loading, also enhanced rubber stiffness (modulus) by acting as an additional loading of carbon black [Shuangye Dai 2007 and A. I. Eatah 1990].

Where as in (100 NR) recipe the tensile modulus increased with carbon black loading level increment without decreasing. From figure (1), also can be noticed that the tensile modulus of SBR increased with NR increment. this is due to NR undergo strain-induced crystallization; the rubbers reinforced each other when subjected to tensile stress, as reflected by a higher tensile modulus obtained in the blend [M.T. Ramesan 2005] and these results are in agreement with the other workers [N. Karak 2000].

The relationship between the ultimate tensile strength and the loading level of the reinforcing filler carbon black (N220) is shown in **Fig. 2** for SBR and NR at different blends. This figure shows that the ultimate tensile strength of all recipes increases with the increase of the loading level of carbon black in a non-linear relationship and maximum value can be

achieved at (60) pphr of carbon black (N220), after that the ultimate tensile strength will decrease with increase of the loading level of carbon black, the cross section of rubber with loading level 80 pphr showed more heterogeneous surface than with lower loading of 20 pphr. The quality of almost every carbon black containing system was highly dependent on the degree of dispersion the carbon black achieved inside the matrix. With increasing filler loading, carbon black aggregates may reaggregate with each other during the process of vulcanization and cause restrictions concerning the ability to wet effectively the carbon black aggregates with polymer. Therefore, further increase in carbon black loading simply creates flaws which initiate the onset of tensile failure. Also it can be seen that addition of (NR) to (SBR) improve ultimate tensile strength because of NR has more reactive sites to form cross-links during vulcanization than SBR, and with increasing SBR content the cross-link density decreased [Shuangye Dai 2007, A.N. Gent 2001 and D. Salimi 2009].

The relationship between the elongation percentage at break and the loading level of the carbon black (N220) are shown in **Fig. 3** for SBR and NR at different blends. This figure shows that maximum values of the elongation at break were obtained at 40 pphr loading for all recipes. After that elongation-at break (%) decreases gradually with increasing filler loading. The reduction of elongation-at-break is due to stiffening of the polymer matrix by the filler. Further increase in filler loading causes the molecular mobility decrease due to extensive formation of physical bond between the filler particles and the polymer chain that stiffen the matrix. The increase in filler loading leads the matrix progressively becoming reinforced and hence lowering elongation-at-break at any filler loading greater than 40 pphr [A.N. Gent 2001]. The elongation at break is reduced by increasing the SBR content. This is because molecular weight of NR is higher than that of SBR [Sung-Seen Choi 2007].

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show the (shore (A) and IRHD) hardness plotted against the loading level of carbon black (N220) for all recipes of (SBR/NR) respectively. From these figures it can be seen that rubber hardness shows significant increment with the increasing loading level of carbon black (N220) in a non-linear behavior but at different rates in each Durometer tester. Hardness increases as filler content increases come from the fact that as filler content increases, the crosslinking density increases which make the filled vulcanizate harder than the gum vulcanizate [Pham Thi Hao 2001].

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show that the rate of hardness increases with (SBR) loading level increment and the maximum rate of hardness can be obtained with (100 SBR), SBR has sterically hindered phenyl groups and higher affinity towards Carbon black, the hardness of unfilled SBR higher than hardness of unfilled NR, this may due to SBR is a copolymer of butadiene and styrene and acts as a harder Component to increase the degree of the hardness of the SBR [N. Karak 2000 and D. Salimi 2009].

Fig. 8 shows the wear rate versus the loading level of carbon black for all recipes. These figures show that the wear rate of all recipes is inversely proportional with the loading level of carbon black and the relationship is non-linear. Wear resistance of rubber can generally be enhanced by introducing reinforcing filler into the matrix material. The explanation is that the sliding of abrasives on a solid surface result in volume removal, and wear mechanism depends on the hardness of the composite component which is a key parameter in governing the amount of material removal, so that the presence of the hard reinforcing filler increases the effective hardness of the composite which acts to reduce the amount of material removal [Mayyadaha Shanan Abed 2008]. **Fig. 9** shows that, increment the wear resistance of (NR) with increasing the amount of (SBR). This is because of the hardness

of SBR higher than hardness of NR, which mentioned before, and abrasive wear higher depends on hardness. **Fig. 10** shows the resilience percentages versus the loading level of carbon black for all recipes. These figures show that the resilience percentages of all recipes are inversely proportional with the loading level of carbon black and the relationship is non-linear. This is due to *firstly* the reinforcing filler interferes with rubber chains and it impedes the mobility of flexible chains when they are subjected to stress. Also the interfered fillers could shorten the length of very long chains which leads to the decrease of the rubber elasticity and then resilience. Therefore when the loading level of the reinforcing fillers is increased, its effect increases. *Secondly* hardness of rubbers increase with carbon black increment, that give it maximum ability to absorb the energy, and less ability to returned it as kinetic energy again [Issam S 2006].

It can be seen from **Fig. 11**, increment the resilience percentages of (100 SBR) with increasing the amount of (NR). This is because NR has resilience higher than SBR because strain-induced crystallization made NR more elastic than amorphous SBR i.e. the rebounded impact energy of NR more than SBR. This is in agreement with other works [Mayyadaha Shanan Abed 2008 and Issam S 2006].

CONCLUSIONS:

The addition of carbon black (N220) to the rubbers (SBR and NR) and their blends and the addition NR to SBR leads to improve the mechanical and physical properties, the conclusions are:

1. Ultimate tensile strength, modulus of elasticity increased with the increase of the loading level of the carbon black for the SBR / NR recipes at specific limit and maximum value achieved at 60 pphr , elongation percentages at break decreases with the increase of the loading level of the carbon black, and all these properties increased with adding NR to SBR.
2. Hardness of rubber composites increases with the loading level of carbon black and reaches a maximum value of (87 IRHD) and (89 Shore A) for SBR reinforced with 80 pphr carbon black. The hardness of NR increase with addition of SBR.
3. Abrasive wear rate is reduced by addition of carbon black; this is due to hardness increment with increase carbon black. SBR reinforced with 80 phr carbon black has the best abrasive wear resistance at value (1.7816).
4. Resilience decreases with the addition of reinforcing filler (carbon black), and The minimum resilience (maximum damping) character of SBR reinforced with (80 pphr) carbon black was (29.8%). Also the addition of NR to SBR Increase the resilience.
5. The optimum blend which achieved moderate between properties is (50 SBR/50 NR) loaded with 60 pphr carbon black.

Table 1: The Compound Formulations

Item	Material	Loading level (phr)				
		100	75	50	25	0
1	SBR	100	75	50	25	0
2	NR	0	25	50	75	100
3	Zinc oxide (activator)	5				
4	Stearic acid (activator)	2				
5	Antioxidant	1.5				
6	Antiozonant	1.5				
7	Process oil	5				
8	Carbon black (N220)	(20, 40, 60, and 80) phr				
9	Sulphur	5				
10	Accelerator (TMTD)	2				
12	Reclaim	5				

Item No.	Description
Stage (1) Master Batch	
1	Passing rubbers through rolls several times with decreasing a mill roll opening to 0.5cm, at 70C°.
2	During whole operation, cutting of milled rubber diagonally, rolled or spiraled, and passed into nip in horizontal and vertical state alternatively several times for homogenization.
3	Adding reclaimed rubber to the milled rubber with mill opening 2.5cm to 0.5cm for several times, and repeat item (2).
4	Adding of Stearic acid and zinc oxide.
5	Adding of antidegradants, and repeat item (2).
6	Adding half of each carbon black and process oil, and repeat item (2).
7	Adding the other half of each carbon black and process oil, and repeat item (2).
Stage (2) Final Batch	
8	Cooling the master batch to the room temperature.
9	Adding the accelerator.
10	Adding the sulfur to the master batch.
11	Sheeting the batch to a thickness of (0.5) cm.
12	Cooling the batch to room temperature rapidly to prevent pre-vulcanization.

Fig.1: Tensile Modulus at 100 Elongation versus Loading Levels of Carbon black (N220) For SBR/NR Recipes.

Fig. 2: Tensile Strength versus Loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220) For SBR/NR Recipes.

Fig. 3: Elongation at break versus loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220) For SBR/NR Recipes.

Fig. 4 : Hardness Shores (A) Versus Loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220) For SBR/NR Recipes.

Fig. 5: Hardness (IRHD) Versus Loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220) For SBR/NR Recipes.

Fig. 6: Hardness Shores (A) Versus NR at Different Loading Levels of Carbon Black.

Fig. 7 : Hardness Shores (A) Versus NR at Different Loading Levels of Carbon Black.

Fig. 8 Wear Rate versus Loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220) For SBR/NR Recipes.

Fig. 9 : Wear Rate versus NR at Different Loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220).

Fig. 10 : Resilience Percentage versus Loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220) For SBR/NR Recipes.

Fig. 11: Resilience Percentage versus NR at Different Loading Levels of Carbon Black (N220).

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